

Justus Liebig University - Gießen

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Professor Dr. Stefan Peters

On the European Road to Energy Transition in the Western Balkans

by

Dragan Simonovski

Abstract:

This paper presents an analysis of energy transition and sustainable development efforts in the Western Balkans region, particularly in the context of European integration. It examines the challenges and opportunities faced by the six countries of the bloc: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia and Kosovo, in aligning with EU norms and standards related to clean energy, decarbonization and environmental protection. The paper questions whether the European Union's policies are the right choice for the Balkan regions' energy transition by comparing key indicators such as economic inequality, fuel consumption, and air quality in an attempt to assess the region's progress and shortcomings in achieving sustainable energy systems in comparison to those already achieved by EU member states. The findings of this work highlight the importance of a just transition and the need for tailored approaches that take into account socio-economic impacts and local dynamics. It also discusses the impact of EU policies, such as the European Green Deal and the Energy Union Strategy, on energy transition efforts in the Western Balkans. It concludes by highlighting the importance of localized and dynamic strategies to ensure a successful and inclusive energy transition in the region.

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On the European Road to Energy Transition in the Western Balkans

“Different roads sometimes lead to the same castle.”

–George R. R. Martin¹

Introduction

Is the way to the EU the right track for the Western Balkans in the context of the energy transition?

The countries of the Western Balkans have a long-term goal of joining the European Union. They have all signed stabilization and association agreements with the EU, which aim to promote stability and cooperation in the region as well as pave the way for eventual EU membership. The norms and standards of the EU that have to be undertaken by the countries in the region include energy transition, clean energy, and fossil fuel consumption decline as a means of decarbonization². Therefore, this work would aim to analyze and question the energy transition trends and directions taken by the countries of the Western Balkans as a whole, a region that is outside but aspires to be a part of the European Union, through the lens of the research question posed at the beginning of this chapter. We would make an attempt to assess the current processes aimed at implementing sustainable development activities in the region of the Western Balkans and the ones already implemented in the EU from the datasets available, as well as other research papers on the topic.

The Western Balkans in this paper refer to the 6 countries in the region of south-eastern Europe that are not member-countries of the European Union but have committed to being integrated: “Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, and Kosovo.”³ All the countries except Kosovo have been officially granted candidate status, and three of the six Western Balkan states are members of NATO (Albania, Montenegro, and North Macedonia).

¹ From the book *A Game of Thrones* (1996).

² The Renewable Energy Directive of the EU, revised in 2023 and now referred to as RED III, set a target for the share of renewable energy sources (RES) in EU energy consumption of 42.5% by 2030. This goal refers to an EU average, while Member States set their own national contributions to the target.

³ Bartlet, W. (2008). *Europe’s Troubled Region: Economic Development, Institutional Reform and Social Welfare in the Western Balkans*. Routledge.

Fig. 1: Current EU accession status of the Western Balkan countries

Courtesy of the The International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance, from the *Journal of Geography, Politics and Society* 2022, 12(2), 36–50

In recent years, the Western Balkans region has made efforts to line up with EU standards and regulations in various policy areas, including energy transition. “All accession agreements signed by the EU with third-party countries generally aim to gradually develop the free trade zone, to improve economic relations, to develop political dialogues between the EU and signatory countries, as well as to initiate the gradual approximation of the laws and regulations of the Member States and signatory countries.”⁴ As the EU continues to prioritize sustainability and renewable energy initiatives, the question arises: is the path to EU membership the most advantageous direction for the Western Balkans’ economies in terms of energy transition? This paper seeks to explore the potential benefits and challenges of EU integration of the Western Balkan countries in the context of energy transition. By examining the current energy policies and experiences in the region, as well as the practices in the EU, considering the socio-political dynamics at play, and having the concept of just transition in foresight, this research aims to provide insights into whether the EU standards’ course is the right path for the Western Balkans to achieve their energy transition goals.

⁴ Nezirović, S., Živko, A., Durmišević, B., & Hodžić, A. (2022). Stabilisation and association agreement between the Western Balkan countries and the European Union. *Journal of Geography, Politics and Society*, 12(2), 36–50. p. 37

Background

The Balkan Peninsula has been the ground for rapid societal changes in the last decades of the XX century, as well as the first two decades of this one. The turbulent history and frequent conflicts leading to instability and intermittent periods of peace, often with the advocacy of international organizations and governments, have taken their toll on the economic sector all throughout the region, directly influencing the processes of sustainable development.

The aftermath of World War II brought about a significant shift in global power dynamics, with the emergence of new players on the world stage. The Soviet Union, for instance, rose as a formidable force, challenging the dominance of the capitalist West. This led to the division of Europe into two opposing blocs, each seeking influence and control in the post-war era. The Balkans were immersed in the eastern socialist bloc. This meant renewal and recovery from the ruins that the war left in a rather different way than that of the capitalist west, led by the 'great powers,' dominated by the United States of America and the United Kingdom. This does not necessarily mean that it was a bad thing. On the contrary, if you ask many of the elders in the region of the Western Balkans, one would get the answer that "back in the day," the standards were higher, the economy was better, and the environment was cleaner. A possible explanation for this frame of mind could be the extended, in many cases unjust transition in which previously established norms were simply eradicated by the emerging oligarchy.

Mencinger remarks that "the transition has proven to be a painful process with many setbacks, and social and political tensions emerging from the redistribution of income, wealth, and power. This could have been expected; the transition began without a clear picture of the actual situation, without a fully worked-out scheme for a new economic system, and without a suitable economic and social arrangement in place. They were replaced by assumptions that the elimination of deformed non-market institutions, restoration of private ownership, together with a laissez-faire free market mechanism, would instantly transform socialist countries into welfare states. New, mostly inexperienced governments were assisted by international financial institutions; many domestic politicians and foreign advisers were ideologically and politically motivated, with their major goal being the abolition of socialism and existing institutions rather than the gradual creation of a viable economic system and increased economic prosperity for everybody. In short, previous prevention of »capitalist exploitation ideology« was replaced by what George Soros called »market fundamentalism«.⁵

The transition had also, unfortunately, brought war and famine to the region. "The post-socialist countries are, by the standards of the EU, poor countries. The major

⁵ Mencinger, J. (2013) From the Collapse of Socialism to the Crisis of Capitalism: Experiences of Central and Eastern European Countries. *Ljetopis socijalnog rada*, 20 (1) 7-30. University of Ljubljana Faculty of Law Economic Institute p. 24

developmental task facing these countries is, therefore, that of catching up with their more prosperous neighbours.”⁶

Decades have passed now, and while not all wounds from the recent wars and conflicts have been healed, communities went on to unite on the path of fast economic development, which for most of them meant integration within the euroatlantic structures, most of all the EU and NATO. Some of the most important challenges in this context are the implementation of norms and standards in the legislative and economic spheres, as well as the fulfillment of the energy transition goals and policies of the EU, which are generally focused on balancing economic growth with environmental supervision and social equity. Efforts to promote green technologies, enhance energy efficiency, and foster sustainable practices are gaining momentum as countries in the region attempt to build resilient and inclusive economies for the future. The path towards sustainable development in the Balkans is marked by a commitment to overcoming historical legacies and embracing innovative solutions that prioritize the well-being of both present and future generations.

Fig.2 : Western Balkan’s Strategic and Legislative Frameworks on Energy and Climate

	Energy Strategy	Low-carbon Development Strategy	Climate-change Law	Energy Efficiency Strategy	Renewables Development Strategy
Albania	National Energy Strategy 2018-2030	National Climate Change Strategy (endorsed in 2019)	Law on Climate Change (adopted in December 2020)	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan expired in 2020	National Action Plan for Renewable Energy Resources in Albania 2019-2021
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Framework Energy Strategy 2035	Climate Change Adaptation and Low Emissions Growth Strategy 2025	-	Action Plan for Energy Efficiency of Bosnia and Herzegovina 2019-2021 (NEEAP BiH) (final draft)	National Renewable Energy Action Plan 2020
Kosovo	Energy Strategy 2017-2028	Climate Change Strategy 2019-2028 and Action Plan on Climate Change 2019-2021 (approved)	-	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) 2019-2021 (draft)	National Renewable Energy Action Plan (NREAP 2011-2020)
North Macedonia	Energy Development Strategy 2030	Long-term Strategy on Climate Action and National Action Plan on Climate Change (drafts)	Law on Climate Action (draft)	Fourth National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) (adopted)	Renewable Energy Action Plan Until 2025
Serbia	Energy Sector Development Strategy for the Period until 2025; Energy Development Strategy 2040 (draft ongoing)	Draft low-carbon development strategy	Law on Climate Change (adopted in 2021)	Fourth National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) (until 2021) (adopted)	National Renewable Energy Action Plan 2020 (adopted in 2013)

Source: OECD, *Multi-dimensional Review of the Western Balkans, From Analysis to Action*, April 2021, section 14.2 (Green: valid documents, black: requires revision, blue: documents are drafted but not approved, red: document expired)

⁶ Dyker, D. A., & Radošević, S. (2001). Building social capability for economic catch-up: The experience and prospects of the post-socialist countries. *Innovation*, 14(3), 219–237.

Theoretical Approach

The energy transition, a key component of sustainable development, involves shifting from fossil fuel-based energy systems to renewable and clean energy sources. The European Union has been at the forefront of promoting energy transition through its ambitious climate and energy targets, such as the European Green Deal⁷ and the Energy Union Strategy⁸. By committing to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, increase energy efficiency, and boost renewable energy production, the EU aims to transition towards a low-carbon and sustainable energy system. The European Commission has set up a rather ambitious plan to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by the year 2050.⁹

The Western Balkan countries, comprising Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, and Kosovo, have all signed Stabilization and Association Agreements with the EU, signaling their commitment to aligning with EU norms and standards. As aspiring EU members, these countries are expected to adopt and implement EU energy and environmental policies, including those related to energy transition and clean energy. Therefore, a logical inquiry arises into whether the normatives and standards set by the EU for energy transition and sustainable development of the Western Balkans are an attempt to maintain social engineering in the 'less developed' area or whether they represent objective, rationally and scientifically proven methods for the future of the region. The theoretical framework for this study is based on the concept of sustainable development and the priority of energy transition within the context of European integration, through discourse analysis and comparison. The European Union's norms and standards, particularly those related to energy transition, clean energy, and the reduction of fossil fuel consumption, serve as the guiding principles for a critical understanding of the present state and trajectory that is posed on the Western Balkan countries' sustainable development initiatives. The EU's policy framework for sustainable development and energy transition is of crucial importance in understanding and assessing the energy transition trends and directions taken by the Western Balkans. By gaining insight into the current situation in this field for the member countries of the EU and comparing it to the position the countries in the Western Balkans are in, we can grasp the possible implications of European integration and the stabilization and association agreements for the energy and environmental policies of the Western Balkan countries. Thus, by drawing on existing research, policy documents, scholarly literature, and statistics, this work aims to

⁷ The European Green Deal is a set of proposals to make the EU's climate, energy, transport, and taxation policies fit for reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels.

⁸ The Energy Union Strategy is a project of the European Commission to coordinate the transformation of European energy supply. It was launched in February 2015, with the aim of providing secure, sustainable, competitive, and affordable energy.

⁹ EC Strategy and policy, priorities 2019-2024:

https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

establish a theoretical foundation for the comparative analysis of sustainable development activities in the Western Balkans and the EU in an attempt to demythologize the challenges deep-rooted in the region's pursuit of harmonization with EU standards and practices.

Three road signs

Illustration by the author

For the purpose of understanding the pathway taken and the trajectories of the Western Balkan societies in the energy transition undertaking, three important indicators for the region can be of immense importance: economic inequality, fuel consumption and pollution—more specifically, air quality.

While most of the available studies and analyses on this issue take into consideration the GDP per capita as one of the key indicators of 'green' quality, this study uses the economic inequality rate as an indicator. The importance of economic inequality as a means of a just transition is very high since "the fact that inequality, even more than poverty, harms everyone

in society.”¹⁰ This concept covers inequality in income, wealth, and consumption trends. The dimension of inequality is important when studying or examining just transition because it shows how wide the gap between the rich and poor is and contributes to the persistence of poverty. This can become a giant obstacle, endangering justice and equality within the process of energy transition, especially considering that the uneven distribution of resources can have more severe impacts that spread through various sectors, including education, health and even socio-economics, as well as peace and stability.¹¹

Another important road sign would be the fuel consumption rate for the production of energy. With a comparison of the trends considering the energy dependency and the share of energy from renewable sources in the EU member-states decades and the ones in the region of the Western Balkans, we can summarize and conclude whether the measures undertaken by the countries that are already in the Union have given fruit and whether this is the right pathway for the countries aspiring to join the European family. This is an important indicator because the transition of the Western Balkans’ carbon-intensive economies implies decarbonisation, while most of these same economies are dependent on the resources of oil and lignite.¹² EU policies enforce the use of renewable sources and clean energy.

When it comes to pollution, measured through the air quality index, we can wittingly conclude that it is intertwined with the previous indicator - that of fuel consumption. The striking data that most (98%) of the European population lives in areas exceeding the World Health Organization’s recommended annual levels for PM2.5 particles, the pollutant most closely associated with premature mortality¹³ details the urgency of assessing and addressing this issue.

Economic Inequality

The issue of economic inequality for the region taken into consideration has a wider span and context than only economics. A thorough analysis of inequality, poverty and poverty perceptions in the Western Balkans, both on a micro and macro level, by the International Monetary Fund finds that there is “persistent dissatisfaction among people in much of the region. Those who grew up in the former Yugoslavia remember a time when they lived well and could travel freely abroad. The uncertainty and vulnerability of the transition period are in sharp contrast with this experience and appear to be driving dissatisfaction even following years of

¹⁰ Van Niekerk, A. J. (2020) Inclusive Economic Sustainability: SDGs and Global Inequality. *Sustainability*, 12(13), 5427. p.16

¹¹ Galtung, J. (1969) Violence, Peace, and Peace Research. *Journal of Peace Research*, 6(3) pp. 167-191. p.171

¹² Mustata, A. Shevchuk, V. (2021) *Osam koraka ka pravednoj (energetskoj) tranziciji na Zapadnom Balkanu*. CEE Bankwatch Network. p.3

¹³ Fletcher, E.R. (2024) Air Quality in Europe Shows Significant Improvement Since 2003. [Health Policy Watch News](#)

high growth. The crisis likely further worsened the situation as it hit households in the Western Balkans particularly hard, even more so than in Central and South Eastern Europe, resulting in job losses, reductions or delays in wages, and lower remittances. Many more people feel poor in the region than are picked up by standard income-based measures.”¹⁴ In the same line, EBRD’s Transition Report found that up to 40 percent of income inequality in the region is due to factors outside of people’s control, such as place of birth, parental education, and gender.¹⁵

The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development further concludes in a report regarding the living standards in the Western Balkans that “catching up fully with average EU living standards will take several decades at least, and possibly 70 years or more. It is impossible to say with any certainty how long this catch-up process will last, or to be sure that the Western Balkans will one day fully converge on EU living standards.”¹⁶ One should have foresight into the fact that the level of living standards in the region is almost six times lower than the EU’s average.¹⁷

In light of these challenges, Goal 10 of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals stands as a crucial beacon, aiming to eliminate extreme economic inequality by 2030¹⁸. This ambitious target underscores the global commitment to addressing disparities and promoting inclusive growth across regions, including the Western Balkans. Efforts to tackle systemic inequalities and foster sustainable development will be vital in shaping a more equitable and prosperous future for all.

One of the key measurements, the median annual disposable income, refers to the amount of money that an individual or household has available for spending and saving after taxes and other mandatory deductions have been taken out. It is often used as a measure of overall economic well-being and can vary significantly depending on factors such as location, occupation, and education level. In 2022, the highest levels of median annual disposable income were recorded in Central and Nordic EU Member States. By contrast, the median disposable income was lower in most Southern and Eastern member states.¹⁹

¹⁴ Koczan, Zs.(2016) *Being Poor, Feeling Poorer: Inequality, Poverty and Poverty Perceptions in the Western Balkans*. IMF Working Papers.

¹⁵ Bartlett, W, Uvalić, M. (2022) *Towards economic inclusion in the Western Balkans. New Perspectives on South-East Europe*. Palgrave Macmillan. p. v

¹⁶ Tabak P. et al (2022) *Can the Western Balkans converge towards EU living standards?* European Bank for Reconstruction and Development. p. 8

¹⁷ Filipović, S., & Ignjatović, J. (2022). Economic development of the Western Balkans: Opportunities and limitations for Green transition. *Megatrend Revija*, 19(3), 167–182. p. 171

¹⁸ United Nations, [Department of Economic and Social Affairs](#)

¹⁹ All data, maps and charts in this chapter, unless otherwise indicated are courtesy of [Eurostat](#), drawn upon the [EU statistics on income and living conditions \(EU-SILC\)](#)

Fig.3: Median equivalised disposable income, 2022 (PPS per inhabitant)

A noticeable rebound, considering the median annual disposable income, can be seen in Eurostat’s map in the yellow area, depicting exactly the region of the Western Balkans, where the PPS per inhabitant is lower than 9.000 — almost half the European average. Median disposable income provides a measure of average living standards, but it does not capture the distribution of income within the population. The Gini coefficient gives the extent to which the distribution of income within a country deviates from a perfectly equal distribution. A Gini value of 100 means that only one person receives all the income in the country, while a Gini value of 0 means that income is distributed equally across the population. In 2022, the Gini coefficient for the EU was 29.6, which is a new low, indicating that income inequality has fallen in the blocs over the past decade. The highest income disparities among the EU Member States (with a Gini coefficient of at least 34.0) were recorded in Bulgaria (38.4), Lithuania (36.2), and Latvia (34.3). A group of member states with a Gini coefficient above the EU average of 29.6 and ranging

between 31.0 and 33.9 comprised Malta, Greece, Estonia, Spain, Portugal, Romania and Italy. In Croatia, Germany, Cyprus, Luxembourg and France, the Gini coefficients were close to the EU average, indicating income distributions consistent with the EU coefficient. At the other end of the scale, income was more evenly distributed in Slovakia, Slovenia, Czechia and Belgium, where the Gini coefficient was less than 25.0.

*Fig. 4: Gini coefficient for equivalised disposable income per inhabitant, 2022
(Scale from 0 to 100)*

According to the latest data, in the Western Balkans, the coefficient ranged from 31.4 in North Macedonia (2020 data) to 44.2 in Kosovo (2018 data). The Gini coefficient in Montenegro (2020 data) was 32.9; in Albania, 33.2; and in Serbia, 33.3. There was no data available for Bosnia and Herzegovina. These datasets show that the income distribution in the latest measurements was more equal in recent years in all Western Balkans than it had been prior to

2016, as measured by the income quintile share ratio. However, there is still a large difference, compared to the average values of the central European countries, and especially the EU member-states.

Comparisons of further statistics on living conditions in the EU and the Western Balkans show similar proportions. On the basis of the most recent data available, the share of the population at risk of poverty after social transfers in the Western Balkans ranged from 21.2% in Serbia to 27.9% in Kosovo. In the EU in 2021, it was 16.8%. In 2021, the proportion of people aged 18–59 who lived in households with very low work intensity in the Western Balkans ranged from 11.6% in Albania (2020 data) to 38.6 % in Kosovo (2018 data). This ratio was estimated at 9.4% in the EU.

Fuel consumption

Fuel consumption, especially when used for energy production, is a key element of the EU policy agenda. These policies enforce the use of renewable energy sources with the aim to improve energy security; support the achievement of a carbon neutral society, and decouple energy costs from oil prices. Alongside this, EU policy has also supported the development of gas pipelines and electricity transmission networks across the EU, as well as common rules to increase competition between suppliers and promote consumer choice. Energy crises have underlined the EU's need to work with its neighbours on energy security, including diversification of energy sources, routes and suppliers.²⁰ Đurašković et. al note that “the political and economic turmoil of recent decades has greatly influenced the energy supply of the individual countries in the Western Balkans region. Before gaining independence, all the countries, except for Albania, were part of a unified energy system. Most of the countries of the Western Balkan region inherited their energy infrastructure (e.g. for oil, gas and electricity) from the Socialist Federal Republic (SFR) of Yugoslavia, where most of the production plants were outdated and indeed, ripe for reconstruction and the improvement of production efficiency. Thus, one of the main features of the energy systems in the Western Balkans is their low level of energy efficiency, which is primarily reflected in energy losses in electricity distribution. The poorly maintained and aging energy infrastructure results in an energy intensity considerably higher than the European Union average. According to Eurostat, in 2018, 120 kilograms of oil equivalent (kgoe) of energy were needed in the EU-27 to generate EUR 1 000 of GDP, while among the Western Balkans countries, the energy intensity was at least double that of the

²⁰ From the [Energy statistics report for the enlargement countries by the European Commission](#)

EU-27 and was in fact more than three times greater in Serbia, Kosovo, and Bosnia and Herzegovina.”²¹

The latest data considering the energy dependency rate, which shows the proportion of energy that an economy must import and is defined as net energy imports divided by gross available energy, expressed as a percentage, shows that in 2021, only one country among the Western Balkans recorded energy dependencies of more than 50%: North Macedonia (68.0%). The other Western Balkans recorded rates of around 30%: Serbia with 34.8%, Kosovo with 32.6%, Montenegro with 31.1%, Bosnia and Herzegovina with 27.2%, and Albania with 23.8%. It should be noted that a positive dependency rate indicates a net importer of energy, while a dependency rate in excess of 100 % indicates that energy products have been stocked.

Fig. 5: Energy dependency, 2011 and 2021
(% of net imports in gross available energy)

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo Declaration of Independence.
Note: Countries are ranked based on 2021 data.
(*) 2020 data instead of 2021.
(*) 2011 not available.
Source: Eurostat (online data codes: nrg_ind_id)

eurostat

Between 2011 and 2021, the energy dependency rate increased in North Macedonia, Kosovo and Serbia (by 22.4 pp, 5.1 pp, and 4.3 pp, respectively), while in Albania and Montenegro it decreased by 11.9 pp, 5.1 pp, and 0.5 pp, respectively. In the EU, the energy dependency rate decreased from 56.4 % in 2011 to 55.5 % in 2021.

Another measurable parameter in this sphere is the gross energy generation. That is the amount of electrical energy produced by transforming other forms of energy and is expressed in gigawatt hours (GWh). The generation of electricity can vary greatly when the main source is hydro-, wind or solar power. In the period between 2011 and 2021, the countries in the West Balkans have had various trends: Kosovo's electricity generation had an overall ascending trend, Serbia's electricity generation was relatively constant, in Montenegro, electricity generation between 2011 and 2021 recorded an overall increase, while North Macedonia recorded a decrease of its electricity generation. Albania's electricity generation recorded the highest

²¹ Đurašković, J., Konatar, M., & Radović, M. (2021). Renewable energy in the Western Balkans: Policies, developments and perspectives. *Energy Reports*, 7, 481-490.

increase and there is not enough data available for Bosnia and Herzegovina. In the EU, electricity generation decreased slowly between 2011 and 2014 and recovered between 2015 and 2017. Between 2011 and 2021, it recorded an overall decrease of 1.0 pp.

Fig. 6: Share of energy from renewable sources, 2011 and 2021
(% of gross final energy consumption)

We can see that in 2021, Albania, Montenegro, Serbia and Kosovo all had higher shares of renewables in gross final energy consumption than the EU; only North Macedonia had a lower share and no data was available for Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Air Quality

Bosnia and Herzegovina and North Macedonia's capitals are often in the number one position on the top chart of the most polluted cities in Europe, especially in the winter season. The air quality represents a serious indicator, not only for environmental preservation but also for the living standard as well as for human rights. A rapid increase in greenhouse gas emissions was reported for North Macedonia between 2011 and 2012 and has been fluctuating ever since, such that between 2011 and 2019 (the most recent data available), the overall increase was 1.3%. Serbia has recorded an overall decline of 10.0% in greenhouse gas emissions in the same period, while in Bosnia and Herzegovina, there was an overall increase in emissions of 10.9% between 2011 and 2018 (more recent data is not available). Montenegro saw an overall decrease over the period, reaching a level of emissions in 2020 that was 13.1% lower than in 2011.

The index for total greenhouse gas emissions in the EU reflects an overall fall of 17.7% in these emissions between 2011 and 2020.

Fig. 7: Greenhouse gas emissions, 2011-2020 (index 2011=100, based on CO2 equivalents)

Carbon dioxide is one of the greenhouse gasses: while it has the lowest global warming potential, its emissions in the EU are much higher than any of the other six greenhouse gasses. Bosnia and Herzegovina (data to 2018), Montenegro (data to 2019), and Serbia (data to 2014) reported a decline in CO2 emissions, while in the EU in 2021 they were 19.1% below the figure ten years earlier. Data on North Macedonia and Kosovo is not available.

Fig. 8: Carbon dioxide emissions, 2011–2021
(index 2011 = 100, based on tonnes)

In January 2014, the European Commission introduced a 2030 climate and energy framework to stimulate private investment in infrastructure and low-carbon technologies. The framework sets ambitious targets, including reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 40% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels and aiming for renewable energy to account for at least 27% of consumption by 2030. The Commission also proposed reforms to the emissions trading system and potential adjustments to the energy efficiency directive. In November 2018, the EU unveiled its 2050 long-term strategy to transform Europe into the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050, in response to urgent climate and environmental challenges.

Subsequently, in December 2019, the European Commission introduced the European Green Deal, an action plan aligned with the 2050 strategy that includes further reductions in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030, increased investments in research and innovation, and the protection of Europe's natural environment. A crucial component of the EU's efforts towards climate neutrality is the Fit for 55 package, a comprehensive plan to enshrine climate objectives into EU law. This package consists of a series of proposals to amend existing legislation and introduce new initiatives, focusing on areas such as enhancing energy efficiency and promoting renewable energy sources.

The EU Green Deal aims to achieve “no net emissions of greenhouse gasses by 2050, economic growth decoupled from resource use, and no person and no place left behind. The

Green Agenda is a similar roadmap for the countries of the Western Balkans to adapt to these EU climate targets. Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia all committed themselves to the Green Agenda at the Sofia Summit in November 2020. The Green Agenda is structured along five pillars: cleaning energy sources and protecting the climate; moving to a circular economy; depolluting air, water, and soil; building sustainable agriculture and food systems; and protecting biodiversity and ecosystems. However, implementation is oftentimes lacking due to the perceived financial, economic, and social costs of the transformation processes, diverging interests of societal actors, information gaps among decision-makers, and insufficient regional cooperation. A green transition, especially in the field of energy, is inevitable in order to tackle the climate crisis, mitigate its effects, and ensure future economic development and competitiveness, as well as social justice and cohesion.²²

Taking the right road

As James Ferguson concluded in 1959, the question of what development is “would have made no sense even a century ago.”²³ However, as Ferguson continues, it seems to us today almost nonsensical to deny that there is such a thing as ‘development’ or to dismiss it as a meaningless concept.” Although the integration of the Western Balkan countries into the European Union gives away a sense of an eurocentric development plan for the region, Europeanization and enlargement are two distinct processes. Fagan and Sircar argue that “Europeanization is a longer-term social as well as political and economic transformation that will occur before and after enlargement has occurred. Whether associated with enlargement or not, Europeanization is often defined in rather prosaic terms that conjure a diffusion of norms, changes in behaviour, and an element of practical application. It is usually understood as the impact on domestic politics and public policy of EU laws... the diffusion of norms, values, and behaviours within a candidate state, or indeed a neighbouring country, may well have occurred prior to progress with regards formal compliance. Conversely, an applicant state may have successfully adopted various tenets of the *acquis* and enshrined within the domestic legal system compliant laws, but the process of Europeanization, defined in terms of political process or the way politics is undertaken, may be judged to be limited. Recognizing such a distinction between legal and institutional adaptation on one hand (formal compliance), and political behaviour and process on the other, is critical. This is particularly so in studies of

²² *Green Agenda for the Western Balkans The Road Toward Effective and Sustainable Implementation. (2022).* Aspen Institute, Germany.

²³ Ferguson, J. (1994). *The Anti-Politics machine.*

post-communist accession where formal change is (and has proved to be) far more readily and easily achieved than changes in the style and process of governance.”²⁴

At present, the *acquis*, which represents the body of law, common rights, and obligations that is binding upon all EU member states, is comprised of 35 negotiating chapters, each one covering a distinct area with which the candidate country must align itself via reforms and adaptation of administrative and institutional infrastructures in order for a draft accession treaty to be drawn up. Chapter 27 of the *acquis* concerns the environment and outlines the EU’s environmental policy, which aims “to promote sustainable development and protect the environment for present and future generations” and is centered around a number of core principles. In stipulating that Western Balkan nations must comply with the *acquis*, the EU provides a significant boost to the green transition in the region through encouragement of the adoption of measures regarding areas such as environmental protection and the broader requirement for Western Balkan economies to develop sustainably if they want to maintain hopes of membership.²⁵

Energy poverty remains a pressing concern in the region, with high indicators pushing low-income households towards cheaper yet more polluting energy sources for heating. Existing policies in the Western Balkan countries fall short of effectively addressing energy poverty. A comprehensive approach encompassing short- and long-term measures is needed to improve the financial situation of poor households, encourage energy savings, and enhance protection for vulnerable customers. Efforts aimed at safeguarding the most at-risk groups, such as women, children, and minority populations, from the effects of energy poverty should include incentives for promoting energy savings. A successful green and just transition hinges on phasing out of coal, which requires strategic guidance aligned with national plans to facilitate this shift. A significant challenge lies ahead due to the absence of a comprehensive legal framework for environmental assessment. The Large Combustion Plants Directive, in particular, experienced delays in investment for emissions abatement equipment, exacerbated by the impact of COVID-19 measures, energy price shocks, and the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine. These events raised concerns about supply security, which in turn undermined environmental compliance. In general, respect for the pollution thresholds established by this Directive in the Western Balkans remains low, to the detriment of citizens’ lives, health and the environment²⁶

While the Europe 2020 strategy focuses on reducing poverty, the challenge of reducing poverty risk is linked to inequality. Poverty is measured as the percentage of people living in households with income below a threshold linked to median household income. If poverty falls,

²⁴ Fagan, A., & Sircar, I. (2014). *Europeanization of the Western Balkans: environmental governance in Bosnia-Herzegovina and Serbia*. p.11

²⁵ Philipson, J. (2022). *Driving the Green Transition in the Western Balkans: EU Support and the Facilitation of Renewable Energy Investment*. School of economics and political sciences in Athens.

²⁶ Report on the implementation of the Declaration on energy security and green transition in the Western Balkans (2023). Energy Community Secretariat.

this implies less income inequality as well. The European Pillar of Social Rights presented by the European Commission in April 2017 addresses income inequality more explicitly. The third principle of the pillar sets out equal opportunities for all. Of the fourteen headline indicators in the accompanying social scoreboard, one relates directly to income inequality, while several others address policy areas closely related to combating rising income inequality and providing more equal chances.

Much of what is going on in the current process of enlargement seems to be more than ever connected to politics. This gives away the impression that EU's institutions are deepening the gap between their imposed standards and the practices in the Western Balkans, making the road already taken unstable and the whole process unpredictable. Specifically, recent developments of blocking the opening of the accession negotiations for Albania and North Macedonia by France, Denmark, and the Netherlands have created "disappointment in the two targeted countries and for many fellow Union members enthusiastic about speeding up the enlargement process... Political fragmentation in the EU directly affects the enlargement process. The 2019 impasse was temporarily overcome in March 2020, when the EU's main institutions gave the green light to open the accession talks for the two countries (Council of the EU 2020). But in November, another issue crept up in the process, when the Bulgarian government imposed a new veto, on North Macedonia only... With a bit of irony one could even note that the EU veto decision may have done more than expected in bringing the Western Balkan countries closer to the Union. In fact, three WB countries have responded to the veto with the launch of a "mini-Schengen" proposal (later rebranded as "Open Balkan"), a counter-reaction directed at fostering regional cooperation: the initiative aims at introducing removing visa requirements as well as obstacles to trade of goods and services, eventually realizing regional collaboration plans that have remained only on paper for several years – with Brussels' blessing. The Open Balkan, which at the time of writing has just been officially established, has nevertheless also triggered tensions in the region due to intersecting, long-standing political matters: the pending question of Kosovo's international recognition and the potential overlapping of the Open Balkan with pre-existing EU instruments for cooperation have prevented the participation of all six Western Balkan countries (WB6). Therefore, what is in principle an initiative for more regional integration risks transforming itself into a global showcase for the degree of division and uncertainty still experienced in the Balkans."²⁷

In order to establish sustainable and resilient energy systems, Western Balkan nations have devoted significant focus to the development of renewable energy. The incorporation of renewable energies as a stable source of energy into the energy mix of these nations has the potential to bring about a variety of economic benefits, including a positive impact on local

²⁷ Zoppi, M. (2022). Futures of the Western Balkans. In *SpringerBriefs in Political Science*. p. 10

sustainable development and the prevention of market instability as a result of stable prices.²⁸ However, as Petit proposes - “the world, fueled by inexorable and positive technology development, is moving toward a more decentralized setup, which should be encouraged because of the increased resilience it brings to the fragile construct of living together. Moreover, this more decentralized society will return resources and opportunities to people at a fraction of their cost. In short, this decentralized society is about progress, and with it, greater abundance for all will come.”²⁹

Therefore, energy transition policies must also take into account socio-economic impacts. These vary depending on the sector, region and country. However, the most common impacts relate to the restructuring of industrial systems, job reallocations, and the expenditure associated with switching to cleaner technologies, both in industrial processes and in daily life.³⁰

States and stakeholders in energy projects, energy value chain inputs, or energy systems must not discriminate, whether directly or indirectly, on any ground such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other reason, with regard to decisions relating to energy projects, energy systems or energy value chain inputs in question, including with regard to decisions on how to distribute benefits and burdens arising out of or relating to the energy project, energy system or energy value chain input in question³¹

Conclusion

In the analysis, we have seen that when it comes to the economic inequalities as well as the air pollution, the region should adapt to the ways of the Union, because it lags behind terribly, in most cases, double below the EU averages. This empirically shows how the Western Balkan policies in this area have utterly failed in the past decades, while the ones at play in the European countries have managed to maintain economic inequality at reasonably lower levels, which is a necessary prerequisite if we want to achieve a just transition. However, when it comes to energy dependency and share of energy from renewable sources, data shows that in some instances, the Balkan countries have developed a sense for successful navigation down this road.

By all means, a general conclusion can be drawn that all the plans and measures programmed for the integration of the Western Balkans into the European Union should follow a careful and custom-made approach, free of false discourses and artificially imposed norms.

²⁸ Jakupi, E. H. (2023). *Renewable Energy in Western Balkans: Special focus on solar photovoltaic (PV) systems connected to the distribution network*. RIT.

²⁹ Petit, V. (2021). *Age of Fire is over, the: A New approach to the energy transition*. World Scientific.

³⁰ Wilduto, A. (2023). *Energy Transition in the EU*. EPRS | European Parliamentary Research Service.

³¹ Sourgens, F., Sempretegui, L. (2024). *Principles Of International Energy Transition Law*. Oxford University Press.

The term “Western Balkans” itself did not even exist a few decades ago. It was constructed to depict the ‘otherness’ of a region not entirely incorporated within the European Union's values and standings. Thus, the path to the transformation of the region into a green energy zone, paying attention that no one is left behind, can not be conducted by blindly following policies, normatives and standards that have been developed in an office thousands of kilometers away and which can be easily annulled or postponed when crises or politics come knocking at the door, as we have seen in the previous years. Rather, a different road is welcomed - one that can be adapted, localized and dynamic.

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